

Sphagnum Dances – Merging with Mosses

Vegetal agency in distributed more-than-human choreographies

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ABSTRACT

This paper refers to an ongoing interdisciplinary, art-based research project which aims to question the disembodied rationale of Western epistemology and related regimes of dominant knowledge by focusing on vegetal agency. Following the approach of “Plant Thinking”, sphagnum mosses become the protagonists in this endeavor, as they are to be considered as key regulators of peatland ecosystems resisting the severe consequences of anthropogenic interference such as desiccation. Informed by feminist posthumanism the project aims to transgress the distinction between subject and object by tracing the formation of configurations, where nature and culture construct each other. The project involves two mutually informative art-based strategies of inquiry which both use mimesis as a lens: Based on a period of gathering data via field experiments, interviews and walks with biologists, audiovisual research about peatland and mosses, a laboratory experience space was created which invites the audience to immerse themselves in a living archive of mosses. The second strategy of inquiry addresses the interaction between the audience and the specimens. This is made possible by using artificial intelligence models mediating between the audience and the biomes and communities, the mosses interact with. By training a number of specialized LORA models with the collected hundreds of images of biomes and specimens, we can prompt those AI models to turn participants into plants, fungi, soil and whole ecosystems that move along with them. The project invites to participate in seemingly rational practices of objectification such as collecting, inspecting, sorting and categorizing and juxtaposes them with seemingly affective practices of performance and dance. By activating the entire body to explore the dynamics of vegetal phenomena, the project critically approached the disembodied rationale of Western epistemology thereby exposing the dichotomy of human activity and plant passivity as a myth. The result is a distributed choreography involving human and more-than-human actors.

KEYWORDS

post-humanism, artificial intelligence, art-based research, ecosystems, performance, more-than-human choreographies

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1 Introduction

Peatlands rank among the most important ecosystems on the planet. While they cover only three percent of the world's land area, they store around twice as much carbon as the total biomass of all the world's forests [1]: Anthropogenic changes to the planet, put peatlands under threat. They are drying out because of climate change or are being dried out for agricultural production. Mosses are specialists adapting to challenging conditions. In this context sphagnum mosses represent interesting actors as they are considered as key regulators of peatland ecosystems resisting the consequences of anthropogenic interference. In his work “Plant-Thinking: A Philosophy of Vegetal Life”, Michael Marder [2] argues that plants have habitually been dismissed as mute, unfeeling and passive objects without agency in Western epistemology. According to Marder this anthropocentric viewpoint forms the basis for exploitative practices, which have led to current situation on the planet. He pleads for a shift towards “plant thinking” which includes recognizing the intelligence, agency, and interconnectedness of plant life. As Marder [3] stresses (on p. 196), “plant communities are tangles of stories about interactions among plants, the collaborations and collisions of plants with bacteria, fungi, and animals; agriculture and permaculture; diets and habitats; and less and less so, the wilderness.”

Taking up the attempt to listen to the stories of plants and understand vegetal agency, this project asks mosses to “tell their stories” thereby integrating that subjugated knowledge. As Haraway [4] highlights – despite the view of Western epistemology – science (about nature) is not the source of objectivity, but is also socially constructed, full of biases and storytelling. Following Haarmann’s [5] approach of artistic research, the project aims at exposing the relativity of the researcher’s gaze with the use of aesthetic means.

The project invites to participate in seemingly rational practices of objectification such as collecting, inspecting, sorting and categorizing and juxtaposes them with seemingly affective practices of performance and dance. By activating the entire body to explore the dynamics of vegetal phenomena, the project critically approached the disembodied rationale of Western epistemology thereby exposing the dichotomy of human activity and plant passivity as a myth. The result is a distributed choreography involving human and more-than-human actors. Allying art-based research practices, the project aims at transgressing the boundaries between laboratory and everyday life, the observer and the observed, human and more-than-human, subject and object as well as nature and culture.

2 Applied Artistic Strategies

The project involves two mutually informative art-based research strategies which both use mimesis as a lens [6]. The project operates at the intersection of science visualization and performance transgressing the boundaries between performance and audience. The audience is first invited to participate in seemingly rational practices of objectification such as collecting, inspecting, sorting and categorizing, mimicking science laboratory life. This experimental set-up is then juxtaposed with seemingly affective practices of performance and dance, where the audience merges with the more than human actors inhabiting the biome (mosses, fungi, and soil).

Based on a six-month period of gathering data via field experiments, interviews and walks with biologists, audiovisual research about peatlands and mosses, a laboratory experience space was created which invites the audience to immerse themselves in a living archive of mosses. In the first phase of the project, the relativity of the researching gaze is analyzed with aesthetic means in the sense of critical epistemology. The second phase deconstructs the disembodied rationale of modern society. The practice of research through movement engenders ways of knowledge production as relating, where “knowledge is not anymore considered a discrete human affair that filters an objective

world out there, it is embedded in the ongoing remaking of the world”, p. 28 in [7].

2.1 Laboratory Experience Space

The participants enter an experience space, which mimics a laboratory and epitomizes a living archive. The lab includes several workstations which, in their entirety, form an interactive multiscreen installation. Live feeds from two microscopes and a camera rig are displayed on large screens. The audience can engage with those instruments and explore a variety of specimen, as well as two living biomes within terrariums.

The installation space makes it possible for the audience to interact with methods that are vital to the art-based research process – exploring fascinating microcosms through technologies and processes that are normally confined to the (scientific) laboratory. The diverse structures, patterns and colors of photogrammetrically recorded mosses are displayed on screens.

Through techniques of microscopic zooming in and out, the reversal of perspectives and the stage-like staging of the moss, the installation breaks with the idea of objective distance to the object of research. As agency is being distributed among apparatuses, animals, plants and humans, the boundaries between objectification and subjectification dissolve.

While scientific cataloguing practices claim to show and preserve, these exhibits are aesthetic artefacts. Using microscopy processes and interactions are captured that would otherwise remain invisible. Instead, an “aesthetic reality of facts as artefacts” emerges, as Haarmann [8] states.

Figure 1: Mimicking the laboratory: Techniques of zooming in and out enable participants to develop different perspectives on mosses.

2.2 Distributed Performance - Merging with Mosses

The second strategy developed within the project focuses on the interaction between the audience and the specimens at the center of the research process. This is made possible by using artificial

intelligence models mediating between the audience and the biomes studied. By training a number of specialized LORA models with hundreds of images of the biomes and specimens observed and studied, those AI models were prompted to turn participants into plants, fungi, soil and whole ecosystems – in real time. Participants' body movements in front of a large projection are tracked and “mimicked” by the AI models – turning their mirror image into ever evolving ecosystems that move along with them.

Figure 2: A participant's movements in front of a large screen are tracked and mimicked by the AI models resulting in a performance.

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